

Shilajit Odour : Its Origin and Chemical Character^ψ

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The chemical nature and composition of the odorous constituents of shilajit, from six countries, were determined. Collection of the volatiles from the headspace by a special technique, followed by GC MS and CI MS analyses showed the presence and relative abundance of about two dozen compounds common to all shilajit samples, albeit in different proportions. These compounds belonged to four distinct classes, viz. (i) long-chain aliphatic hydrocarbons and their derivatives at different states of oxidation, (ii) naphthenes (alkylated cycloalkanes), (iii) alkylated aromatics and phenolics and (iv) heterocyclics. Phospholipids of shilajit, isolated and characterised by selective chemical treatment and FAB MS analysis, contributed (as fixerators) to the stability of its odour. This study dispels the age-old myth regarding the composition of the 'typical' odour and reaffirms our earlier postulate about the origin of shilajit.

Shilajit, a pale-brown to blackish-brown exudation of variable consistency, intimately associated with steep rocks (at altitudes of 1000–5000 m) of different formations, is found throughout the world. It is also found embedded in rock sediments and is exposed after erosion of rock surface-horizon or after landslide and excavation. In the Himalayas, it occurs almost ubiquitously from Arunachal Pradesh in the East to Kashmir in the West. Several other mountain ranges in India, e.g. the Aravallis, the Eastern Ghats and the Vindhyas, are also rich repositories of shilajit. It has also been encountered in mountains of other countries, viz. Afganistan (Badakh-Shan), Australia (Northern Pollock), China (Xinjian), Nepal (Dolpa), Pakistan (Hindukush), and the Republics of the erstwhile USSR (e.g. Tajikistan, Khaburabao-Pamir)¹. Shilajit is used in Oriental medicines as a panacea^{1,2}. The therapeutic effects of shilajit, as determined by the modern scientific studies, are the consequences of hormonal control and regulation of immunity³.

Considerable controversy had existed in the literature^{2,4} when we initiated the study of shilajit about twenty years ago⁵. Shilajit then was variously described, such as, a bitumen, an asphalt, a

plant fossil exposed by the elevation of the Himalayas, inorganic minerals, and as a substance of unknown origin^{2,4}. The polemics persisted⁶ until we found cogent evidence³ that shilajit was composed of fresh and modified remnants of humus-paleohumus, admixed with low molecular weight (low M_r) plant and microbial metabolites, e.g. phenolic acids, oxygenated acetophenones and dibenzo- α -pyrones and phytosteroids in free and conjugated states^{1,5,7}. The humic substances constitute 10–70 per cent of the water-soluble fraction of raw shilajit³. The variations in the proportion of humic substances are due to several geological and pedological factors associated with the source rocks⁷.

Shilajit exudes a 'typical' odour which is described in the ancient texts⁸ as *gomutra*-shilajit (meaning smell of cow's urine). This odour is believed also to contribute to the healing and rejuvenating (*resayana*) properties of shilajit⁸.

Until this investigation, the origin and chemical character of this 'typical' odour were obscure. It was not known whether this odour was derived from microbial putrefaction, or from contamination of animal urine of mountain habitats or from

^ψPart 17 in the series 'Shilajit'. For Part 16 see Ref. 15.

distribution of each class of compounds in the different shilajit samples. This would ensure standardisation of the odorous chemicals in unexplored shilajit samples.

The hexane-solubles of shilajit exhibited $[M-H]^-$ peaks, with assignments in parenthesis, at m/z 105 (dimethyl/ethylbenzene), 119 (trimethyl/methylethyl/propylbenzene), 131 (tetralin), 133 (diethyl/dimethylethylbenzene), 137 (*trans*-decalin), 141 (methylnaphthalene). These aromatic compounds constituted about 2–12% of the high volatile constituents of shilajit. Major portions (70–80%) of the volatiles were, however, aliphatic hydrocarbons and were not detected by this selective CI-hydroxyl ion spectral analysis (see also Experimental). The detection and identification of the aliphatic hydrocarbons were accomplished by determining the composite spectra and also from enfleurage chromatography. The remaining 10–25% of the volatile constituents were naphthenes (alkylcycloalkanes), alkyl- and alkylaryl alcohols, aldehydes and acids, naphthalenes, and heteroaromatic compounds (Table 1).

The formation and metabolism of humic substances of terrestrial and aquatic origin, in general, and of shilajit in particular, are currently understood^{1,7,13} as a complex series of biochemical-geochemical transformations (within the source rocks in case of shilajit) in their natural habitats. By the geochemical transformation sequence, the products of *exo*- and *endo*-enzymatic reactions of microorganisms, algae, lichens, and of higher plants are further converted into petroleum intermediates and products. Incorporation of these transformed entities into the micropores (voids)^{1,7} of shilajit humus and their protection within the shilajit sheath from extraneous onslaughts are only natural phenomena^{1,3}.

We believe, that, these aroma constituents of shilajit, in appropriate formulations, would find specialised application, e.g. in aroma therapy, an emerging area in phytotherapy. What can be measured and subjected to analysis in the projected

shilajit aroma therapy is the electromagnetic signal(s) triggered by these chemicals within the different regions of the CNS (central nervous system). Various behavioural, physiological and biochemical changes produced, after the odour has been perceived, can be determined.

One might wish to peruse the current state of shilajit in the Indian market. Manufacturers of proprietary products, containing shilajit as a single entity or as a constituent of a composite

TABLE 1—NATURE AND COMPOSITION OF THE HEADSPACE VOLATILES OF SHILAJIT^a

Compd.	Relative abundance per cent ^b	
	Source : Nepal (Himalayas)	India (Vindhyas)
<i>Aliphatics :</i>		
n-Undecane	3.76	27.96
n-Dodecane	6.68	24.70
n-Tridecane	2.40	26.10
1,1-Dimethoxyoctane	6.82	—
2,6-Dimethylnonane	—	2.31
4-Methyldecane	+	4.61
6-Methylheptanol	8.57	+
n-Nonanal	7.52	+
n-Decanal	4.95	—
2-Ethylhexanoic acid	2.72	+
<i>Naphthenes :</i>		
Methylpropylcyclohexane	12.31	1.15
Diethylcyclohexane	—	+
<i>Aromatics :</i>		
1,3-Dimethylbenzene	7.27	0.78
2,4-Diethylbenzene	—	0.96
1,2-Dimethyl-4-ethylbenzene	4.06	—
1-Isopropyl-3-methylbenzene	+	1.22
1-Methyl-4-propylbenzene	0.75	—
Naphthalene	6.17	+
<i>trans-Decalin :</i>	+	0.96
<i>p</i> -Cresol	15.02	+
3/4-Ethylphenol	7.50	+
2,4-Bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)phenol	0.14	+
<i>Heterocyclics :</i>		
Benzothiazole	1.35	+
2,4-Dimethylquinoline	1.93	9.29

^aCollection of headspace volatiles for 40 h showed strongest response in GC MS analysis.

^bArea per cent normalised to equal a sum total of 100%. (+) denotes traces ($\leq 0.01\%$); —, denotes not detected.

preparation, are blissfully unconcerned about the modern aspects of characterisation and standardisation of shilajit. Consequently, the literatures available with their products are full of incontinent claims and disinformation. The shilajit products are often found to be contaminated with ballasts of microbial debris, fungal toxins and polymeric quinones which pose considerable risk from a public health viewpoint. Another important criterion often missed or ignored is the judicious ingestion of shilajit along with modern medicines, particularly in geriatric population. Simultaneous administration of shilajit and modern drugs is distinctly contra-indicated in several situations¹⁴.

silica capillary column (OV-1 50 M × 0.32 mm) was used. Several headspace attempts were made on each sample as the intensity of the runs were very weak due to tenacious retention of the volatiles by the shilajit mass. Collections for a period of 40 h provided optimum results (Table 1).

Selective CI-MS analysis of the volatile aromatic compounds of shilajit : Chemical ionisation (CI) of a hexane solution of shilajit, in which ions produced under a high pressure reagent gas (from electron impact-N₂O-hexane combination in the ion source)¹⁰ reacted selectively with the alkylaromatic compounds, sparing the aliphatic hydrocarbons. Distinctive product ions were produced from the benzylic-H containing alkylaromatic compounds. These were characterised from their respective [M-H]⁻ peaks (vide *supra*).

Isolation of phospholipids of shilajit : In a typical experiment, finely powdered and dried shilajit was exhaustively extracted with hot n-hexane. The straw-coloured gummy residue, obtained from the hexane extract, was kept under vacuo, at 37 ± 2°, for a week to remove the high volatile constituents. The non-volatile product was subjected to FAB-MS analysis.

Deacylation of the non-volatile product was carried out, in anhydrous methanol using catalytic amount of fresh NaOMe (0.2 N), according to a previously described method¹². The pentane-soluble fraction from the deacylated reaction product, containing methyl esters of fatty acids, liberated from the phospholipids, was subjected to GC-MS analysis. The residue left after pentane extraction, was acidified (HCl), cooled, and neutralised (NH₄OH), in succession. The liberated *lyso*-derivatives afforded glycerophosphorylcholine and glycerophosphorylinositol, whose identities were established as before¹².

FAB-MS analysis of phospholipids of shilajit : Argon was used as the primary beam; the spectrum was obtained at an accelerating voltage of 3 kV. The ion source was maintained at ambient temperature. The hexane extractives were

TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF PHOSPHOLIPIDS^d OF SHILAJIT

Compd no	FAB-MS (M + H) <i>m/z</i>	EI-MS Fragment ions, <i>m/z</i> (Assignment)
1	745	577 ^b , 339 ^c , 265 (oleoyl), 239 (palmitoyl), 86, 71 (choly)
2	743	575 ^b , 337 ^c , 265, 263 (linoleoyl), 239, 237, 86 71
3	769	605 ^b , 367 ^c , 335 (phosphatidylinositol), 239, 222 (gadeleoyl)

^dIsolated from n-hexane extract of shilajit according to a published procedure²¹

^bFragmentation at x. ^cFragmentation at x and y (see Fig. 1).

Experimental

Shilajit : The test samples, used in this study, were either collected by the author during several sojourns to the respective countries and/or obtained through the courtesy of appropriate scientific authorities. Their authenticities were verified by hplc and hptlc finger-prints^{1,3}.

Analysis of headspace volatiles of shilajit : A well-documented procedure⁹ was followed. Briefly, shilajit was placed in a two-armed flask equipped with a Tenax trap on one arm; through the other arm, the flask was purged with purified air. The volatile constituents liberated from shilajit were collected on the trap and subsequently desorped into a gas-liquid chromatograph for further analysis by GC-MS spectroscopy. Fused

applied to a stainless-steel probe tip with an appropriate amount of glycerol. The probe was immediately inserted into the mass spectrometer. Appropriate synthetic derivatives of phospholipids (markers) were used for standardisation purpose. The results are incorporated in Table 2.

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